

DESIGN OF BIDIRECTIONAL POWER CONVERTER FOR ELECTRIC VEHICLE APPLICATION

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Abstract— Batteries are the primary energy-storage devices in ground vehicles. Now days battery fed electric drives are commonly being used for electric vehicles applications, due to various advantages, such as: nearly zero emission, guaranteed load leveling, good transient operation and energy recovery during braking operation. To fulfill these requirements converters with bidirectional power flow capabilities are required to connect the accumulator (battery) to the dc link of the motor drive system. Battery fed electric vehicles (BFEVs) is required to function in three different modes namely: acceleration mode, normal (steady-state) mode and braking (regenerative) mode. During acceleration and normal modes, the power flow is from battery to motor whereas during braking or regenerative mode the kinetic energy of the motor is converted into electrical energy and fed back to battery. The DC-DC converter is required to perform mainly two functions: first to match the battery voltage to the motor rated voltage and second to control the power flow under steady-state and transient conditions, so that the drive performance is as per the requirement. In the present work closed loop operation of bi-directional dc-dc converter feeding a dc motor and its energy recovery due to regenerative braking has been demonstrated. The characteristics of battery operated electric vehicle under different drive condition are also presented. The effectiveness of the system is verified through the simulations using Simulink/ MATLAB 7.6.0 (R2014a) package.

Keywords— DC-DC Converter; BLDC Motor; Battery

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently bi-directional dc-dc converters are widely researched and developed for various applications such as battery charger dischargers, electric vehicles and UPS systems. In case of the battery fed electric vehicles (BFEVs), electric energy flows between motor and battery side. For achieving zero emission, the vehicle can be powered only by batteries or other electrical energy sources. Batteries have widely been adopted in ground vehicles due to their characteristics in terms of high energy density, compact size, and reliability. This can be applied in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (HEVs) with a battery as an energy storage element to provide desired management of the power flows. In hybrid electric vehicle energy storage devices act as catalysts to provide energy boost. However, the high initial cost of BFEVs as well as its short driving range has limited its use. Bidirectional dc-dc converters are the key components of the traction systems in Hybrid Electric Vehicles. The use of a Bi-directional dc-dc converter fed dc motor drive devoted to electric vehicles (EVs) application allows a suitable control of both motoring and regenerative braking operations, and it can contribute to a significant increase the drive system overall efficiency. Recently many Bidirectional dc-dc converter topologies have been reported with soft switching technique to increase the transfer efficiency. Bi-directional converters using coupled inductor were introduced for soft-switching technique with hysteresis current controller. For minimizing switching losses and to improve reliability, zero-voltage-switched (ZVS) technique and zero-current-switched (ZCS) technique were introduced for Bi-directional converter. A multiphase Bi-directional converter is suitable for high power application. To achieve high voltage rating or current rating more number of converters can be connected in series or parallel with low switching frequency. A unified

current controller (Zhang et al, 2008) was introduced for Bi-directional dc-dc converter which employs complementary switching between upper and lower switches.

This paper deals with the use of a Bi-directional dc-dc converter for a battery fed electric vehicle drive system. A closed loop speed control technique of the proposed battery fed electric vehicle is designed and implemented using PI controller. The overall drive system reduces the system complexity, cost and size of a purely electric based vehicular system.

Figure1 shows the proposed Bi-directional dc-dc converter fed DC motor drive. In this topology, boost converter operation is achieved by modulating Q2 with the anti-parallel diode D1 serving as the boost-mode diode. With the direction of power flow reversed, the topology functions as a buck converter through the modulation of Q1 with the anti-parallel diode D2 serving as the buck-mode diode. It should be noted that the two modes have opposite inductor current directions. A new control model is developed using PI controller to achieve both motoring and regenerative braking of the motor. A Lithium-ion battery model has been used in this model to verify the motor performance in both motoring and regenerative mode. This controller shows satisfactory result in different driving speed commands.

2. THE NEED FOR A BIDIRECTIONAL DC-DC CONVERTER IN THE EV IS DUE TO THE FOLLOWING REASONS.

- 1) The system is operating at the high power and low voltage making the current to rise too high, which causes high electrical and thermal stresses in the passive as well as the active components of the system, also it increases the ohmic losses and hence decrease efficiency.
- 2) Device voltage and current stresses is even further increased up by the wide variation in the input voltage range of the system. Since device stresses depends on the output to input voltage ratio, input voltage variation further increases the components ratings to be used.
- 3 Further along with the above two factors, the parasitic ringing due to the parasitic components causes EMI emission and therefore, the proper shielding has to be provided. All above three factors makes the converter packaging bulky, heavy and expensive. Thus there is a need for an efficient DC-DC converter to deal with this issue.
- 4) To be able to recharge the electrical energy storage system during the re-generative braking, and hence therefore there should be the provision of bidirectional power flow.

Some of the requirements for the Bidirectional DC-DC converters design for the HEV applications are as follows

- Lightweight & compact size
- Lower electromagnetic Interference
- Lower input and output current ripple
- Controlled power flow in spite of wide input voltage variation”.

3. BIDIRECTIONAL DC-DC CONVERTER WITH BATTERY AND DC MOTOR

Fig.1: Proposed Bi-directional dc-dc converter fed DC motor drive

In this topology, boost converter operation is achieved by modulating $Q2$ with the anti-parallel diode $D1$ serving as the boost mode diode. [With the direction of power flow reversed, the topology functions as a buck converter through the modulation of $Q1$ with the anti-parallel diode $D2$ serving as the buck-mode diode. It should be noted that the two modes have opposite inductor current directions. A new control model is developed using PI controller to achieve both motoring and regenerative braking of the motor. A Lithium-ion battery model has been used in this model to verify the motor performance in both motoring and regenerative mode. This controller shows satisfactory result in different driving speed commands

CONVERTER OPERATING MODES

The MOSFETs $Q1$ and $Q2$ are switched in such a way that the converter operates in steady state with four sub intervals namely interval 1($t0-t1$), interval 2($t1-t2$), interval 3($t2-t3$) and interval 4($t3-t4$). It should be noted that the low voltage

battery side voltage is taken as $V1$ and high voltage load side is taken as $V2$. The gate drives of switches $Q1$ and $Q2$ are shown in Figure. The circuit operations in steady state for different intervals are elaborated below. Interval 1($t0-t1$): At time $t0$, the lower switch $Q2$ is turned ON and the upper switch $Q1$ is turned OFF with diode $D1$, $D2$ reverse biased as shown in Figure 2(a). During this time interval the converter operates in boost mode and the inductor is charged and current through the inductor increases. Interval 2($t1-t2$): During this interval both switches $Q1$ and $Q2$ is turned OFF. The body diode $D1$ of upper switch $Q1$ starts conducting as shown in Figure 2(b). The converter output voltage is applied across the motor. As this converter operates in boost mode is capable of increasing the battery voltage to run the motor in forward direction. Interval 3($t2-t3$): At time $t3$, the upper switch $Q1$ is turned ON and the lower switch $Q2$ is turned OFF with diode $D1$, $D2$ reverse biased as shown in Figure 2(c). During this time interval the converter operates in buck mode. Interval 4($t3-t4$): During this interval both switches $Q1$ and $Q2$ is turned OFF. The body diode $D2$ of lower switch $Q2$ starts conducting.

Fig.2: Converter Operating Modes

Interval 2($t1-t2$): During this interval both switches $Q1$ and $Q2$ is turned OFF. The body diode $D1$ of upper switch $Q1$ starts conducting as shown in Figure 2(b). The converter output voltage is applied across the motor. As this converter operates in boost mode is capable of increasing the battery voltage to run the motor in forward direction.

Interval 3($t2-t3$): At time $t3$, the upper switch $Q1$ is turned ON and the lower switch $Q2$ is turned OFF with diode $D1$, $D2$ reverse biased as shown in Figure 2(c). During this time interval the converter operates in buck mode.

Interval 4($t3-t4$): During this interval both switches $Q1$ and $Q2$ is turned OFF. The body diode $D2$ of lower switch $Q2$ starts conducting

4. CONTROL STRATEGY

The control circuit of the bidirectional converter is shown in Fig. to control the speed of the dc drive; one possible control option is to control the output voltage of the bidirectional converter. To control the output voltage of the bidirectional converter for driving the vehicle at desired speed and to provide fast response without oscillations to rapid speed changes a PI controller is used and it shows satisfactory result. In this control technique the motor speed ω_m is sensed and compared with a reference speed ω_{ref} .

The error signal is processed through the PI controller. The signal thus obtained is compared with a high frequency saw tooth signal equal to switching frequency to generate pulse width modulated (PWM) control signals.

Fig.3: Control strategy of the bidirectional dc-dc converter.

Fig. 4: Closed loop operation of the drive.

The block diagram of feedback speed control system for DC motor drive is shown in Figure; the control objective is to make the motor speed follow the reference input speed change by designing an appropriate controller. The proportional-integral (PI) controller is used to reduce or eliminate the steady state error between the measured motor speed (ω_{motor}) and the reference speed (ω_{ref}) to be tracked.

• *Parameter used in the Simulation*

The Separately excited DC motor rated at 5HP, 240V, 1750RPM

Bidirectional converter parameters are: $L=1600 \mu H$, $C_H=470 \mu F$, $C_L=470 \mu F$, $f_{sw}=20 \text{ kHz}$

Battery voltage = 48V, Battery capacity = 16Ah, SOC= 88%

5. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

- For Normal Condition Torque:- 10Nm, ref. speed- 120rad/sec:

Motor Results

Battery Results

- For Motoring Condition Torque:- 10Nm, Ref. Speed:- 60rad/Sec To 120rad/Sec:

Motor Results

Battery Results

- For Braking Condition Torque:- 10Nm To -10Nm, Ref. Speed:- 60rad/Sec To 120rad/Sec:

Motor Results

Battery Results

6. CONCLUSION

We have studied a battery operated electric vehicle system and it shows satisfactory performance at different driving condition. The proposed control technique with PI controller find suitable for this electric drive. The performance of the BFEV is verified under forward motoring mode, regenerative mode and when there is step change in speed command.

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